

Flexible metal-oxide thin film transistor circuits for RFID and health patches

P. Heremans^{1,2}, N. Papadopoulos¹, A. de Jamblinne de Meux^{1,2}, M. Nag^{1,2}, S. Steudel¹, M. Rockelé, G. Gelinck³,
A. Tripathi⁴, J. Genoe^{1,2}, K. Myny¹

¹imec, Kapeldreef 75, B3001 Leuven, Belgium, email: heremans@imec.be

²University of Leuven Department ESAT, Kasteelpark Arenberg 10, B3001 Leuven, Belgium,

³Holst Centre, High Tech Campus 31, 5656AE Eindhoven, The Netherlands

⁴National Centre for Flexible Electronics, IIT Kanpur, Kanpur-208016 India

Abstract — We discuss in this paper the present state and future perspectives of thin-film oxide transistors for flexible electronics. The application case that we focus on is a flexible health patch containing an analog sensor interface as well as digital electronics to transmit the acquired data wirelessly to a base station. We examine the electronic performance of amorphous Indium-Gallium-Zinc-Oxide (a-IGZO) during mechanical bending. We discuss several ways to further boost the electronic transistor performance of n-type amorphous oxide semiconductors, by modifying the semiconductor or by improving the transistor architecture. We show analog and digital circuits constructed with several architectures, all based on n-type-only amorphous oxide technology. From circuit point of view, the discovery of a p-type amorphous semiconductor matching known n-type amorphous semiconductors would be of great importance. The present best-suited p-type is SnO, but it is poly-crystalline in nature and shows some ambipolarity due to the presence of n-type SnO₂. In search of a better p-type semiconductor, preferably amorphous, we present recent insights into the band structure of potential amorphous oxide p-type semiconductors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Amorphous oxide semiconductors [1] have reached the maturity required for backplanes of active matrix OLED displays. They can be processed directly on flexible plastic substrates, and thus enable mechanically flexible electronics. The electronic performance of circuits is determined by the circuit architecture, transistor device topology and semiconductor material. We discuss the present state of art and future tracks of all three levels. The target application is a health patch as presented in Fig. 1, in which all circuits are thin-film and flexible. Sensor input is processed by analog electronics, and a Near-Field Communication (NFC) circuit transmits the data to a reader. The patch is passive, *i.e.*, it has no battery and the power is harvested from the reader.

II. MECHANICAL VS ELECTRONIC PERFORMANCE OF A-IGZO

To study the mechanical performance of a-IGZO, TFTs with staggered bottom-gate configuration (called ‘ESL’ for etch-stop-layer) were fabricated on 25- μm thick planarized PEN substrates with a recipe described in ref. [2]. As the TFT is on top of a 25- μm substrate, bending imposes tensile strain on the active layer. The amount of strain for each bending

radius was estimated by modeling of the stack. The transistors have a carrier mobility of 12 cm²/Vs, a subthreshold slope of 330 mV/decade and a threshold voltage of 3V. As shown in Fig. 2, below 1% of tensile strain, the charge carrier mobility is almost insensitive to strain. We observed a very small increase of the mobility, estimated to be about 2% ($\pm 1\%$), per % of strain. This is remarkably less than reported values for amorphous Si, polycrystalline Si and organic semiconductors [3]. We ascribe this insensitivity of the mobility to strain to the fact that the electronic conduction in a-IGZO is linked to the orbital overlap between the metal atoms. Mechanical strain slightly changes their atomic positions but does not significantly disturb their orbital overlap. More elaborate investigation confirm a slight increase in overlap in the case of tensile strain [3], in line with the experimentally observed slight increase of the charge carrier mobility.

III. P-TYPE OXIDE TRANSISTORS

A. SnO

For circuit applications, complementary logic is highly beneficial. The performance of the above-described amorphous n-type oxide has so far not been matched with a corresponding p-type oxide material. In the state of the art, sputtered tin monoxide (SnO) is the best p-type oxide semiconductor with reported field-effect hole mobility as high as 4.6 cm²/Vs [4] for discrete devices annealed at 200 °C. Integration in complementary logic with a-IGZO has been shown in [5].

We fabricated staggered bottom-gate SnO TFTs and characterized their performance in circuits. The gate dielectric is 100-nm Al₂O₃ by ALD (specific capacitance of 70 nF/cm²). A 20-nm thick active layer was deposited by thermal evaporation of Sn(II)O powder (97% purity). The layer was annealed in N₂ for 30 minutes at 350 °C. The S/D electrodes were Au patterned by lift-off. As evidenced by GIXRD patterns in Fig. 3, as-deposited SnO is amorphous. No transistor characteristics could be obtained. After annealing at 350 °C in N₂, diffraction peaks appear which can mostly be indexed to the α -SnO phase. Small amounts of SnO₂ and metallic Sn are, however, also present. Transistor characteristics are shown in Fig. 4 (output and transfer curves). The charge carrier mobility in saturation reaches 1.6 cm²/Vs. However, the curves show hysteresis and a significant reverse current, attributed to the presence of n-type SnO₂ in the active layer.

To verify the circuit performance, we constructed 19-stage ring oscillators in diode-load and zero- V_{GS} -load topology, with minimum channel lengths of 5, 3 and 2 micron. The inverter characteristics are shown in Fig. 5, the inverter stage delay versus supply voltage in Fig. 6. Stage delays down to 300 ns, corresponding to a frequency of 83.3 kHz, were obtained.

B. Outlook to future p-type amorphous oxides

Main shortcomings of SnO are its polycrystalline nature and the presence of different phases besides p-type SnO, in particular n-type SnO₂ and metallic Sn. We therefore search for potential alternatives. Candidate p-type oxide semiconductors were screened by ab-initio calculus of a large set of known crystalline phases using as criteria a low effective hole mass in the valence band and p-type dope-ability (*i.e.*, it was verified that intrinsic defects, such as an oxygen vacancy, do not act as hole killers) [6]. When further ruling out toxic materials such as Pb, A₂Sn₂O₃ (A=K, Na), B₆O and ZrOS emerged as the most interesting potential p-types.

We extended the work in [6] by simulating amorphous structures of these materials through a melt-and-quench technique, and studying their electronic structure. A-IGZO is used as reference material, to verify the validity of our approach compared to experiments. Fig. 7 shows its calculated orbitals at the conduction band (CB) and valence band (VB). The wavefunctions at the CB are fully delocalized, confirming that electrons in a-IGZO have a good mobility. Holes at the VB edge, however, are strongly confined. As quantitative measure for the wavefunction delocalization, we plot the Inverse Participation Ratio (IPR) of each electronic state. Near-zero IPR, as required for band-like transport, is confirmed for the CB edge. The valence band edge, however, is decorated with localized (tail) states with high IPR. The case of amorphous K₂Sn₂O₃ is shown in Fig. 8. The wavefunction orbitals at the VB edge are still localized, but less than in a-IGZO. Similar results were obtained for all other high-potential materials listed in [6]: none of the promising crystalline p-type oxides keep good delocalization of holes after amorphization. We conclude that so far, no amorphous p-type oxide semiconductor matching the mobility of n-type a-IGZO could be identified.

IV. ANALOG AND DIGITAL FLEXIBLE CIRCUITS

As no suitable amorphous p-type semiconductor is known, we implement unipolar n-type circuits. We modify the basic ESL transistor structure of Fig. 2a to optimize analog and digital unipolar circuit operation in terms of robustness, gain and gate delay.

The key analog circuit is the A/D converter, and within it, the differential amplifier shown in Fig. 9. The most critical figures of merit for the TFTs in this circuit are the transconductance g_m and the output resistance in saturation R_o . To maximize these figures of merit with n-type a-IGZO TFTs, without adding masks nor process complexity, we introduce a backgate to the structure of Fig. 2a. In Fig. 10, we show the increase in current drive and g_m achievable when biasing the backgate positively. With exactly the same technology, we can also design transistors with increased saturation output

resistance: this is achieved by elongating the overlap of the contact at source side, as shown in Fig. 11. Fig. 12 further shows the achievable output resistances for symmetric transistors compared to designs with large drain overlap or large source overlap. Both the transistor types of Fig. 10 and 11 use the same technology and therefore they can be designed simultaneously in the differential amplifier of Fig. 9, resulting in amplifiers with a measured 14 dB of gain (Fig. 13).

The figures of merit for digital electronics are noise margin and delay of logic gates, like inverters. Also for these figures of merit, the backgate is beneficial [7]. We connect the backgate in elementary inverters to a negative voltage, such that the drive transistor is normally-off (Fig. 14). This very substantially increases the noise margin (Fig. 15) which allows to robustly design circuits with >1E6 transistors (Fig. 15) [7]. Regarding delay, a further improvement can be achieved by modifying the transistor structure to a self-aligned configuration (SAL) with a top gate and self-aligned S/D contacts (Fig. 15). The SAL TFT has negligible gate/source overlap and this leads to about 1 order of magnitude increase in speed. The stage delay of inverters with standard ('ESL') technology (with and without back-gate) versus self-aligned ('SAL') architectures are compared in Fig. 16: 20 ns inverter delay is achievable with SAL. To achieve sufficient robustness in SAL technology for integration of complex circuits, we implement a pseudo-CMOS inverter architecture [8]. We show in this technology (Fig. 17) the code generator of an NFC (13.56 MHz) RFID circuit, clocking data at 396 kbit/s and employing 438 n-TFTs.

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Fig. 1. Target passive thin-film sensor tag, containing analog, digital and RF electronics, to read out a (health) sensor and wirelessly transmit the data to an NFC reader.

Fig. 3. GIXRD patterns of 20 nm thick thermally evaporated SnO_x films: (i) as deposited, (ii) after post-annealing at 350 °C in N₂

Fig. 4 Transfer and output characteristics of p-channel SnO_x TFT.

Fig. 2. (a) a-IGZO ESL device structure ($L=20 \mu\text{m}$; $W=60 \mu\text{m}$) and materials; (b) threshold voltage and subthreshold swing; (c) ON current and mobility as a function of bending strain and corresponding bending radius. Linear transfer curves were characterized at a drain-source voltage $V_{DS} = 1\text{V}$ and gate-source voltage $V_{GS} = 10\text{V}$. Reproduced with permission from [3]

Fig. 5. Voltage transfer curves at various supply voltages for a single- V_{th} diode-load and zero- V_{GS} -load inverter, realized with two p-channel SnO_x TFTs

Fig. 6. Stage delay versus supply voltage of SnO_x unipolar p-type 19-stage ring-oscillator, designed in diode-load and zero- V_{GS} -load logic ($L = 5, 3, 2 \mu\text{m}$).

Fig. 7. Representation of wave function of the first CB and VB of an amorphous IGZO model, and corresponding Inverse Participation Ratio (IPR) of these states, showing delocalized CB and strongly localized tail states near VB. The blue / yellow color of the wavefunction represent its sign.

Fig. 8 Representation of the wave function of the first CB and VB of an amorphous K₂Sn₂O₃ model, and corresponding IPR of the orbitals, showing slight delocalization of the valence band. Nevertheless, these states are still far more localized than the CB in a-IGZO (green horizontal line). The blue / yellow color of the wavefunction represent its sign.

Fig. 9. Schematics of differential amplifier with indication of key transistor parameters

Fig. 13. Measured gain of a-IGZO differential amplifier reaches 15 dB

Fig. 14. Left: a-IGZO TFT with backgate BG: negative BG voltage allows to shift V_T to normally-off. Right: implementation in the inverter topology

Fig. 17. 12 bit RFID transponder clocking at data rate of 396 kbit/s for $V_{DD}=10V$; reproduced from [8] with permission

Fig. 10. a-IGZO TFT with backgate BG: positive BG voltage allows to increase g_m as evidenced by transfer curves below

Fig. 11. a-IGZO TFT with extended source to improve output resistance in saturation (top), compared to symmetric S and D overlaps (below)

Fig. 12. Output resistance as a function of V_G for symmetric overlaps, large drain overlap and large source overlap showing increased output resistance for source overlap

Fig. 15. Inverter characteristics of standard ESL diode-load inverter versus BG-biased inverter of Fig. 14 and (below) corresponding increase in achievable integration density as limited by the soft yield

Fig. 16. SAL a-IGZO TFT structure and stage delay for ESL (standard as well as back-gated) and SAL inverters